

A Data-Driven Lifetime Prediction Method for Thermally Aged SiC MOSFET Applications

Wenfa Kang^{*}, Sen Tan^{*}, Juan C. Vasquez^{*}, Josep M. Guerrero^{*†‡},
Tobias Hertle[§], Thomas Gietzold[§], Andrew Benn[¶] and Baoze Wei^{*}

^{*}AAU Energy, Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark

[†]Catalan Institution for Research and Advanced Studies (ICREA), Barcelona, Spain

[‡]Department of Electronic Engineering, Technical University of Catalonia (UPC), Barcelona, Spain

[§]Collins Aerospace, HS Elektronik Systeme GmbH

[¶]Collins Aerospace, Electronic Control and Motor Systems (ECMS)

Email: ^{*}wka@energy.aau.dk, ^{*}sta@energy.aau.dk, ^{*}juq@energy.aau.dk, ^{*}joz@energy.aau.dk,

[§]tobias.hertle@collins.com, [§]thomas.gietzold@collins.com, [¶]Andrew.Benn@collins.com, ^{*}bao@energy.aau.dk

Abstract—Power semiconductor switches, such as Metal-Oxide Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor (MOSFETs), are widely utilized in solid-state power controllers (SSPC) of electric vehicles, aircrafts and trains. Predictive Health Monitoring (PHM), coupled with the reliability analysis of MOSFETs, are of utmost significance in power electronic systems. Among various PHM indicators, the ON-state resistance of MOSFETs stands out as a vital and indicative harbinger of failure. This paper introduces a data-driven methodology employing a Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) algorithm to predict the variations of the ON-state resistance. The experimental dataset was derived from subjecting the MOSFET to power cycling under thermal stress conditions. Furthermore, the model's efficacy was scrutinized utilizing a minor fraction of the dataset for training the LSTM algorithm, showcasing robust performance. Additionally, the proposed model was validated across diverse MOSFET degradation datasets, affirming its universal applicability.

Index Terms—Solid-state power controller, LSTM, PHM, MOSFET

I. INTRODUCTION

The power Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor Field-Effect Transistor (MOSFET) are widely adopted in various power applications. Research involving leading semiconductor manufacturers, system integrators, and end-users, as noted in [1], [2], has singled out that power electronic devices are the most vulnerable elements in power conversion systems. It reveals that such devices display a greater propensity for failure when compared to passive electrical components, including capacitors and inductors. Moreover, power MOSFETs constitute more than 25% of the market share for power electronic devices, highlighting their critical importance in the sector [1]. Given their extensive deployment and notable failure rates, the prognostics and health monitoring of these transistors are of paramount economic and safety importance.

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The studies documented in [3], [4] show that more than 80% of failures in power MOSFETs happen during their operational periods, and over 90% of these failures are due to fatigue caused by operational stresses. Considering the prevalent occurrence of fatigue-induced failures, forecasting the Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of Power MOSFETs becomes a vital approach for health management and enhancing reliability. When studying the RUL of a MOSFET, a failure precursor, which is defined as a parameter that varies in conjunction with device degradation, serves as an indicator of imminent failure. The methodologies for RUL prediction reported in the literature are fundamentally categorized into two approaches: methods that based on the physical models, and methods that employ input-output data.

The initial approaches, known as model-based methodologies, often focus on analytical models and mechanism of Physics of Failure (PoF). Predominant analytical models in current use include the Lesit model [5] and the Bayerer model [6], noted for their straightforward computation and clear representation. Frequently employed PoF models, such as the energy-based PoF model [7] and the strain-based PoF model [8], are adept at encapsulating the structural characteristics, failure mechanisms, and material attributes of MOSFETs. However, a significant limitation of model-driven approaches is their inability to accurately represent the degradation process. These methods often depend on accelerated aging tests or finite element analysis for parameter derivation, a process that is both costly and time-consuming. Furthermore, the models derived are typically applicable to specific operational conditions, restricting their wide applications.

Prior studies have confirmed that fluctuations in the drain-to-source ON-state resistance ($R_{DS(ON)}$) of MOSFETs act as a principal marker of device failure, stemming from the degradation of wire bonds and the emergence of cracks in the die [9]. Monitoring and forecasting the trajectory of $R_{DS(ON)}$ changes offers a direct assessment of the PHM and RUL of power MOSFETs. In previous study [8], a hybrid prognostics approach that integrates model-based and data-driven algorithms for $R_{DS(ON)}$ prediction, utilizing both an

extended Kalman filter (EKF) as well as a Gaussian process regression (GPR) algorithm. Meanwhile the GPR algorithm delivers accurate predictions in the later stages of device life, it tends to diverge from actual values during the initial phases. Another approach, presented in [10], adopts an empirical model coupled with a Kalman filter to predict the RUL of MOSFETs. Here, the Kalman filter is used to mitigate measurement noise, and the least squares method is applied to predict the RUL, with predicting errors ranging between 0.7% and 28.7%. Afterwards, the authors further enhance measurement accuracy and reduce predicting errors through the application of RANSAC for outlier removal, optimizing the algorithm's parameters via genetic algorithms. This model demonstrates improved resistance to noise; however, it struggles to accurately capture the nonlinear progression of $R_{DS(ON)}$ changes.

This paper introduces a prognostic approach utilizing an LSTM Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to predict the variations in the $R_{DS(ON)}$ of MOSFETs. The inherent feedback connections within LSTM render them exceptionally suited for time series prediction tasks, offering a significant advantage over traditional feedforward neural networks. In this study, we deploy an LSTM framework specifically designed to predict the RUL of MOSFETs, leveraging the predictive modeling of changes in $R_{DS(ON)}$.

II. PROPOSED LSTM-BASED PHM STRATEGY

A. Power Electronics Fault Prediction

Broadly, fault prediction methodologies in power electronics are categorized into four types: 1) component-level analysis, which focuses on the reliability of individual components; 2) damage accumulation models, which estimate wear and tear over time; 3) data analysis techniques, which utilize statistical and machine learning tools to predict failures; and 4) condition-based predictions, which rely on real-time monitoring of system parameters to anticipate faults [11].

Reliability methodologies that concentrate on the component level are not considered prognostic-based because they emphasize variations between individual units instead of their historical usage patterns [12]. The second approach, which typically necessitates experimental testing, yields more precise outcomes for individual units by analyzing the accumulated stress over time [13]. Meanwhile, the third type is the big-data mining based prediction strategy by using the past usage history data, aiming at calculate RUL [9], [14]. Finally, the last method rely on the identification of potential failure modes and the analysis of the underlying causes of failure mechanisms. This is achieved by examining the individual behaviors of units within the physics of the failure model [15].

With the exponential increase in data collected from intelligent devices, traditional approaches encounter challenges in detecting concealed patterns. As a result, leveraging deep learning algorithms for real-time system PHM has become crucial. In this context, the LSTM framework is introduced for predicting the MOSFETs' RUL, offering a sophisticated

Fig. 1. $\Delta R_{ds(on)}$ variations of various MOSFETs (IRF520NPbf).

approach to harness the extensive experimental datasets for accurate prognostics.

B. Key Indicators in Power MOSFET Degradation

Failure mechanisms in power MOSFETs are typically classified into two main categories: extrinsic failures (EFs) and intrinsic failures (IFs). EFs are often due to external factors such as manufacturing defects, handling damage, or adverse operating environments. IFs, on the other hand, originate from the inherent physical and chemical properties of the materials and structures within the MOSFET, leading to degradation over time through normal use.

EFs, the most extensively investigated topics, relate to package-level issues, encompassing problems such as bond-wire lifting, die solder detachment, as well as contact migration. These issues typically arise from external stresses or manufacturing imperfections, affecting the physical integrity and connectivity of the MOSFET components. Research indicates that bond-wire lift significantly impacts device failure over time [16]. According to the most widely accepted industry standards for device qualification, such as AEC-Q101 [17], I_{dss} (Drain current at zero bias), T_j (device junction temperature), V_{th} (gate threshold voltage shifting), R_{th} (thermal resistance of the device), and $R_{ds(on)}$ are identified as the key indicators for tracking MOSFETs degradation. Furthermore, indicator $R_{ds(on)}$ reflects both device characteristics and degradation at the die and package levels, inherently indicating the internal loss of the device [9].

The parameter $\Delta R_{ds(on)} = dR_{ds(on)}/dt$ of various MOSFETs can be observed in Figure 1, which are obtained from the experimental data from by NASA [9]. The degradation patterns of MOSFETs vary due to diverse workloads, environmental conditions, and differences in manufacturing processes. This variability underscores the complexity of accurately predicting MOSFET RUL and performance over time.

Fig. 2. Network structure of an LSTM algorithm.

C. LSTM Network

To predict the RUL/ $R_{ds(on)}$ of MOSFET in a long term, LSTM algorithm is adopted. LSTM, a type of popular deep learning algorithm, addresses the challenges of exploding and vanishing gradients encountered by traditional simple Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). The LSTM architecture comprises three distinct gates: the forget gate, the input gate, and the output gate. These gates ensure the model's effectiveness in analyzing and forecasting sequential time-series data with long-term dependencies, such as predicting stock prices, weather patterns, energy consumption, and lifetime estimates. LSTM networks excel at learning patterns within time series data and leveraging them to anticipate future events accurately.

The LSTM structure is shown in Figure 2. We can observe that within an LSTM cell, three sigmoid (σ) activation functions regulate the information flow and produce signals for the input (i_t), forget (f_t), and output (o_t) gates. These sigmoid gates are activated by inputs derived from the current input signal x_t and the hidden layer h_{t-1} from the previous time step. The cell state c_t is then utilized to capture the information at the current time instant [18].

The LSTM algorithm has the capability to selectively retain and discard information, a process managed by the forget gate. This forget and remember mechanism is implemented using the sigmoid function, which evaluates the current inputs, x_t , and h_{t-1} (the previous hidden state). It generates outputs ranging between 0 and 1, where a value of 0 signifies the complete omission of prior cell state information, and a value of 1 indicates the full preservation of this information.

The mathematical expression of forget gate is

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f x_t + U_f h_{t-1} + b_f) \quad (1)$$

where W_f , U_f , b_f are the weight vectors for forget gate.

The second step involves determining which information should be retained in the cell state. This decision-making process is governed by the input gate layer, which utilizes a sigmoid function

$$\begin{aligned} i_t &= \sigma(W_i x_t + U_i h_{t-1} + b_i) \\ \tilde{c}_t &= \tanh(W_C x_t + U_C h_{t-1} + b_C) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where \tilde{C}_t shows the saved candidate information and W_i , U_i , b_i are the weight vectors for input gate. The update of current cell state c_t can be calculated as

$$C_t = f_t * C_{t-1} + i_t * \tilde{C}_t. \quad (3)$$

The third step is to determine the output information o_t , which is calculated

$$\begin{aligned} o_t &= \sigma(W_o x_t + U_o h_{t-1} + b_o) \\ h_t &= \tanh(C_t) \odot o_t, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where W_o , U_o , and b_o represent the weight vectors for the output gate. The symbol \odot denotes the Hadamard product, which computes the element-wise product. The values for the σ and \tanh functions are computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(x) &= \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}, \\ \tanh(x) &= \frac{1 - e^{-2x}}{1 + e^{-2x}}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Optimization algorithms play a vital role in fine-tuning the weight vectors of LSTM networks, with gradient descent or the loss function being the most commonly utilized method. Additionally, LSTM networks have been trained using optimization techniques such RMSProp and AdaGrad approaches to gradient descent. RMSProp, which is an extension of gradient descent, focuses on adjusting the learning rate, meanwhile AdaGrad adapts the step size for each parameter using a decaying average of past gradients. This paper employs the Adam (adaptive moment estimation) optimization algorithm, which combines the strengths of both RMSProp and AdaGrad. Adam's ability to efficiently adjust learning rates for each parameter makes it a popular optimization strategy in various machine learning endeavors [19].

D. Flowchart of PHM Strategy

As shown in Fig. 3, the general flowchart of designing PHM algorithm for a specific MOSFET normally contains 6 steps. Firstly, specific MOSFET should be chosen for a certain application. Thus, in order to getting degradation dynamics, accelerated life testing experiments should be conducted for the MOSFET. After obtaining testing data, indicators showing degradation dynamics should be identified. Thereafter, in order to reduce the impacts of abnormal data and noises, data preprocessing such as data normalization, filtering and cleaning strategy should be employed. Then, a PHM algorithm is designed to analyze the degradation performance and to provide predicting results of indicators. The predicting results can be used to condition-based maintenance and management.

III. DATA PREPROCESSING

To effectively utilize the relevant experimental data and implement the LSTM algorithm for long-term lifetime prediction, it is essential to undertake thorough data preparation and preprocessing steps. In the data preprocessing, we normally consider data cleaning, data normalization, missing data handling and noise filtering. For the missing data, the estimated

Fig. 3. A general flowchart of PHM algorithm design for SiC-MOSFETs.

data is used by linearized interpolation methods and we use the maximum and minimum to replace the outliers. Also, the data normalization is based on the min-max scaling method expression (6)

$$X_{\text{norm}} = \frac{X - X_{\min}}{X_{\max} - X_{\min}} \quad (6)$$

where X_{norm} is the normalized data, representing voltages and currents of MOSFET. Besides, after data cleaning and normalization, the targeted data is often coupled with measurement noises. Thus, to filter the data, the median filter with a 15-order algorithm is adopted to eliminate the noises in the original data, shown as (7)

$$\text{Median}(x) = \text{median}(f(x+i)), i \in [-N/2, N/2], \quad (7)$$

where x is the coordinates of the data being filtered, and $f(x+i)$ is the filtered value within the sliding window, N is the sliding window size.

After data preprocessing, the drain-to-source voltage $V_{ds,on}$ and drain current I_d of device #36 are shown in Figure 4. It can be observed that drain-to-source voltages of MOSFET vary from 2.2 to 4.5 V over time, meanwhile, the drain current is also changing from 6.5 to 14A. And the $R_{ds(on)}$ can be calculated and shown in Figure 4(c). It can be observed that $R_{ds(on)}$ is changing with the cycle of numbers. The blue curve shows the original degradation data with noises, the red curve is the filtered data by median filter.

The relative performance of predictions can be evaluated using metrics, such as Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), where in this paper RMSE is adopted to validate the performance.

IV. PREDICTION RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section shows the results of MOSFET RUL by using LSTM algorithm. Parameters of LSTM are set as: one layer with 50 neurons, MaxEpochs 10, initial learning rate is 0.1.

The predicting results are shown in figure 5. It can be observed that the prediction error is larger with only 20% training data to train the LSTM network, and RMSE is $8.3e^{-4}$, shown in figure 5(a). Meanwhile in figure 5(b), the predicting curve is closer to the actual curve when training data is increased to 25%. However, the prediction error is still large. If the training data is increased to 40%, it can be observed that the predicting curve is almost the same as the actual curve, which means the prediction error is decreased, shown in figure 5(c). And the REMS is about $3.9e^{-4}$. Figure 5(d) shows the predicting results with 60% training data, it can be seen that the prediction error is much less, with REMS $3.5e^{-4}$.

In another words, the RUL of MOSFET can be calculated by the variation of $R_{ds(on)}$. If the $\Delta R_{ds(on)}$ is increased to 5%, it means that the RUL of MOSFET is zero. Thus, one can obtain the RUL of MOSFET by predicting $R_{ds(on)}$.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the data-driven predictive health monitoring strategy of MOSFET by using LSTM algorithm. Among different degradation indicators, the on-state resistance

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF LSTM ALGORITHM

Layer	Neurons	MaxEpochs	InitialLearnRate	Optimizer
1	50	100	0.1	adam

Fig. 4. (a) drain to source voltage $V_{ds,on}$; (b) drain current I_d ; (c) On-state drain to source resistance $R_{ds(on)}$.

Fig. 5. Predicting results with various training data. (a) Training Data/Testing Data: 20%, $REMS=8.3e^{-4}$; (b) Training Data/Testing Data: 25%, $REMS=6.6e^{-4}$; (c) Training Data/Testing Data: 40%, $REMS=3.9e^{-4}$; (d) Training Data/Testing Data: 60%, $REMS=3.5e^{-4}$.

is chosen as the main indicator to predict the RUL of MOSFET since on-state resistance is capable to present both the die and package level failures. To validate the effectiveness, NASA data set is adopted to obtain the on-state resistance of MOSFET. The simulation results show that the LSTM based strategy can predict the $R_{ds(on)}$ effectively with the increased training data. The future research topic is to design data-driven based online predicting methods.

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